

REINFORCEMENT OF PARTIALLY CURED AEROSPACE STRUCTURES WITH B-STAGED PATCHES

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1 Introduction

The increasing use of composites in aviation and automotive industries has led to increasingly automated production methods such as pultrusion or resin transfer moulding (RTM) for cost reduction in the production of carbon fibre reinforced polymer (CFRP) structures. Textile preform technologies are favourable with relatively simple geometries and constant wall thickness. This paper describes an approach to utilise a basic geometry for several similar parts and add local reinforcement patches only in regions of load introduction or high local stress. The goal of this research is to reduce the cost of assembled composite structures.

This work contributes to the EU FP7 Cost effective reinforcement of fastener areas in composites (CERFAC) programme, where the approach has been applied to the connection of the floor beam (C-beam) to the omega frame of the fuselage, shown in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1. Shows a c-beam to omega frame connection in a fuselage (circled), including reinforcement patches.

In this connection, several rivets will be replaced with a single bolt (concentrated load introduction with a moment free joint). The area of the bolt will be reinforced by a load introducing patch while the

rest of the part will have a nominal thickness that is optimised for bending and tensile stress transfer.

The part and the patch can be produced separately, and the cure may be interrupted at an intermediate B-stage, where the epoxy resin and amine hardener are partially crosslinked.

Later, the patch can be fastened and co-cured onto the part to achieve complete cure in both components, i.e. uniform glass transition temperature, T_g , and matrix elastic Modulus. The co-curing step of this process eliminates a bonding step and results in an ideal monolithic part without using additional structural adhesive, hence the associate preparation costs.

This approach provides the benefit of stress reduction around the hole, simpler geometries of the single parts and high flexibility of reinforcement methods in the patch. The reinforcement can be adapted to the individual load case by the choice of the reinforcement material, layup and resin system. The curing cycle of the part may also be tuned to allow free standing co-cure, therefore providing a cost reduction by freeing a manufacturing tool in a shorter time.

This concept has been studied from resin reaction kinetics to mechanical testing of single bolt connections. Hence, it is necessary to predict the degree of cure, α , and T_g evolution for any time/temperature profile. The influence of the interrupted curing cycle on the mechanical and thermal properties has also been investigated. Another crucial issue in co-curing of B-staged parts relates to surface preparation since many of the usual methods are not applicable in partially cured

resin With abrasive methods particles could be transferred to the resin, and cleaning solvents can easily diffuse into the resin, hence an alternative approach was studied. Lastly, the bearing properties of single-bolt single lap connections are reported.

2 Materials and Methods

The resin used is a monocomponent resin system consisting of a tetrafunctional epoxy resin and two amine hardeners, ‘Hexflow RTM 6’, Hexcel, UK, commonly used in the aerospace industry. The plates were manufactured from a biaxial stitched non-crimp fabric, ‘ECS6090 Series HTS 40’, Saertex GmbH Co., Germany, with an area weight of 256 g/m². Quasi-isotropic plates were made from 16 plies: 2[0/90, +45/-45, 90/0, -45/+45]_s to produce 3.8 mm thick plates. The CFRP plates were cured at 4 bar for varying times at 160 or 180 °C, depending on the desired α . Completely cured CFRP plates were cured at 180 °C for 90 min in accordance with [1].

Reinforcing CFRP patches were manufactured from a thin ply material, ‘20 mm tape, 80 g/m² HTS carbon fibre’, Oxeon AB, Sweden. Quasi-isotropic 2 mm thick, 30 mm diameter, Ø 6 mm hole patches were made from 24 layers of the spread tow with the layup: 3[45, 90, -45, 0]_s. The patches were cured at 30 bar for varying times at 160 °C. The plates and the patches were cooled to stop the curing reaction at a desired value of α . The intermediate degree of cure was tuned such that during co-curing (i) the resin of the patch would still flow while a consolidation pressure is applied via a consolidation jig (i.e. remain below the gel point at $\alpha = 0.59$ [2] and (ii) the plate may be co-cured free-standing.

Bearing samples were manufactured as shown in Fig. 2: CFRP plates were manufactured by an RTM

process, and CFRP patches from thin ply material were produced using a Compression RTM (CRTM) process. For both processes, tools for the manufacturing of bearing samples were designed and manufactured. Both tools have features to directly integrate holes in the composite parts. With the directly positioned and precise tolerance holes, drilling and reaming steps may be avoided for cost savings. The B-stage curing is done using a press with precise temperature control and fast cooling to interrupt the crosslinking reaction. Next, the patch was offered to the plate with a co-cure jig, applying a pressure of 11 bar for the duration of the co-curing (3 mm stroke possible with jig) in a fan assisted oven.

Cure kinetic modelling of the resin was conducted to allow the prediction of α and T_g for the composite sample during the curing cycle. The cure kinetic models were based on data from isothermal and constant heating rate differential scanning calorimetry (DSC) measurements using a ‘DSC Q1000’, TA Instruments, USA. The development of the model is described in more detail in the following chapter.

Single lap bearing test were conducted on CFRP plates, and patch reinforced CFRP plates in accordance to procedure B of ASTM D5961 [3].

Surface characterisation of the of B-staged CFRP plates was conducted using X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS) using a ‘Phoibos 100 MCD’, SPECS GmbH, Germany.

Fig. 2. B-stage co-cure process for producing patch-reinforced bearing samples.

3 Modelling

Pure resin samples of RTM 6 were heated in isothermal or constant heating rate conditions using a DSC. From the measured heat flow, dH/dt , the exothermic peak caused by the curing reaction was integrated, giving the heat of reaction corresponding to ΔH_{iso} and ΔH_{dyn} respectively from the isothermal and dynamic measurements shown in Table 1.

Table 1. Heat of reaction of the isothermal and dynamic DSC measurements.

Isothermal temperature T_{iso} (°C)	Reaction enthalpy ΔH_{iso} (J/g)	Heating rate (°C/min)	Reaction enthalpy ΔH_{dyn} (J/g)
120	392	1	438
120	393	1	438
140	407	2.5	457
140	418	2.5	443
160	435	5	415
160	432	5	412
180	443	10	425
180	450	10	419

The ultimate heat of reaction, ΔH_{ult} , corresponding to a degree of cure α of 1, was determined from the dynamic DSC measurements at 2.5 °C/min, giving $\Delta H_{ult} = 449.75$ J/g. With this value the evaluation of α with time was then calculated as follows:

$$\alpha_t = \frac{\int_0^t \frac{dH}{dt}}{\Delta H_{ult}} \quad (1)$$

For the glass transition temperature T_g modelling, partially cured pure resin samples were measured in a DSC in temperature modulated mode. Using a modulated mode allowed the (reversible) glass transition and start of the (irreversible) residual curing to be separated and analysed. The degree of cure of the samples was calculated as:

$$\alpha = 1 - \frac{\Delta H_{res}}{\Delta H_{ult}} \quad (2)$$

where ΔH_{res} is the residual heat of reaction obtained from the irreversible heat flow of the measurement. The T_g was measured from the inflection point in the step transition in the reversible heat flow. The results of the measurements are shown in Table 2.

Table 2. Measurements of partially cured pure resin samples and partially cured RTM composite plates.

Pure resin samples		RTM plates	
Degree of cure, α	Glass transition temperature, T_g (°C)	Degree of cure, α	Glass transition temperature, T_g (°C)
0	-16	-	-
0.25	8	-	-
0.34	26	0.38	31
0.40	54	0.43	47
0.57	82	0.63	97
0.71	126	0.68	115
0.83	169	0.75	148
0.88	187	0.79	153
0.90	197	0.92	206
0.97	215	-	-

3.1 Glass transition temperature model

The T_g model is needed for optimising the free standing co-cure cycle. For the modelling of T_g as a function of α , the DiBenedetto model [4] in the form introduced by Pascault and Williams [5] was used:

$$T_g = T_{g0} + \frac{(T_{g\infty} - T_{g0})\lambda\alpha}{1 - (1 - \lambda)\alpha} \quad (3)$$

where T_{g0} and $T_{g\infty}$ correspond to the T_g of the uncured and the completely cured resin and were measured as -15.5 and 215 °C respectively, and λ is a parameter, optimised by a least square fit with the data shown in Table 2. The co-curing occurs at high degrees of cure, above 0.7 for the plate. In this region, the T_g is underpredicted with the measured $T_{g\infty}$. To optimise the model fit, $T_{g\infty}$ was also allowed to vary, leading to the parameters in Table 3.

Table 3. Parameters of the DiBenedetto model [4]

T_{g0} (°C) (measured)	$T_{g\infty}$ (°C) (calculated)	λ (calculated)
-15.5	245	0.5052

The resulting model is shown in Fig. 3, achieving a good fit of T_g above an α of 0.7 (region of interest for precise prediction during free standing co-cure).

Fig. 3. Correlation of the glass transition temperature, T_g , and the degree of cure, α

3.2 Cure kinetic model

For modelling the kinetics of the curing reaction, a model described by Ruiz [6] was chosen after comparing different models. This model is based on the Bailleul model [7]:

$$\frac{d\alpha}{dt} = k_1 e^{-E_1 \left(\frac{T_{ref}}{T} - 1 \right)} \sum_{i=0}^m a_i \alpha^i \quad (4)$$

where k_1 is the frequency factor of the curing reaction, E_1 is the activation energy, T_{ref} is an arbitrarily chosen temperature in the operating range, and $G(\alpha)$ is a polynomial of order n function. This model is extended with an n^{th} order term: $(1 - \alpha)^n$. By replacing 1 with $\alpha_{max}(T)$, which accounts for vitrification occurring at higher α and slowing down the reaction, the Ruiz model [6] is obtained:

$$\frac{d\alpha}{dt} = k_1 e^{-E_1 \left(\frac{T_{ref}}{T} - 1 \right)} \cdot \sum_{i=0}^m a_i \alpha^i (\alpha_{max}(T) - \alpha)^n \quad (5)$$

where $\alpha_{max}(T)$ is a model correlating a maximum achievable α to the isothermal curing temperature, and n is a parameter obtained by a least square fit. For determination of the parameters the isothermal measurements were used. A methodology for finding the parameters (k_1 , E_1 , T_{ref} , and a_0 - a_i) of the Bailleul model has been described previously in [7] and was adapted for the fitting in this work. The value of n was obtained using a sum of least squares fit for all measurements.

3.3 α_{max} model

The α_{max} model was obtained by defining a maximum achievable degree of cure, α_{max} for each isothermal temperature. By relating α_{max} with the cure temperature, T_c , instead of relating α with T_g , the DiBenedetto model (equation 3) can be used for predicting α_{max} by solving for α instead of T_g and setting the variable $T_g = T_c$:

$$\alpha_{max} = \frac{(T_c - T_{g0})}{(T_{g\infty m} - T_{g0})\mu + (1 - \mu)(T_c - T_{g0})} \quad (6)$$

where the parameters μ and $T_{g\infty m}$ were fit to the obtained α_{max} values using a sum of least squares fit. T_{g0} is the measured value shown in Table 3.

All the parameters of the kinetic model are summarised in Table 4.

Table 4. Summary of the parameters for the kinetic model

Name	Symbol	Value
Frequency factor	k_1 (s^{-1})	$4.36553 \cdot 10^{-4}$
Activation energy	E_1 (-)	17.107
Reference temperature	T_{ref} (K)	433
Reaction exponent	n (-)	0.04
Polynomial parameter	G_0 (-)	0.1377
Polynomial parameter	G_1 (-)	2.9714
Polynomial parameter	G_2 (-)	-1.1668
Polynomial parameter	G_3 (-)	-19.736
Polynomial parameter	G_4 (-)	75.072
Polynomial parameter	G_5 (-)	-105.77
Polynomial parameter	G_6 (-)	48.567
T_g of the uncured resin (measured)	T_{g0} (K)	257.5
T_g of the completely cured resin (fit)	$T_{g\infty m}$ (K)	458
Adjustable parameter	μ (-)	0.3

The resulting model fit is shown in Fig. 4. The model fits well to the DSC data, even though the vitrification in the low heating rates is not depicted by the model. Note that the most important measurement is at 160 °C, since the first stage of the cure for part and patch are made at this temperature.

Fig. 4. Comparison of the Ruiz model to measured DSC data.

The model fails to predict α at very high conversions (above 0.96). The reason for this could be that in the model only one Arrhenius term describes one overall reaction without taking into account that there are two hardeners and secondary reactions occurring at high α , which would need to be split and characterised independently for more precise modelling.

3.4 Curing cycle simulation

With the kinetic and the T_g model, different curing cycles could be studied. A free-standing co-cure of the CFRP part may be achieved maintaining a part T_g above the curing temperature for the duration of the co-curing. At the same time, the intermediate α should be as low as possible for better resin flow during co-curing. The resulting curing cycle used for producing the CFRP plates is shown in Fig 5.

Fig. 5. A simulated curing cycle for a CFRP part.

The curing cycle of the CFRP patch is defined such that the patch must be cured enough, that (i) it may be handled at room temperature and (ii) α should be as low as possible and importantly, below ($\alpha_{gel} = 0.59$ [2]). Therefore, an isothermal cure at 160 °C to $\alpha = 0.3$ was used to B-stage and then co-curing was followed as per the part. The corresponding curing cycle for the patch is shown in Fig. 6. Note that the T_g of the part is always above the curing temperature during co-curing, so that the resin will not soften, whereas the T_g of the patch is below the curing temperature during co-curing, and the resin soften to liquid. Applied pressure during co-curing, and flow or resin is utilised to achieve a good adhesion of the CFRP patch to the CFRP part.

Fig. 6. A simulated curing cycle for a CFRP patch.

4 Results and Discussion

4.1 Comparison full cure and interrupted cure

To check the influence of the interrupted curing cycle on the thermal and mechanical properties, a plate cured at 180 °C was compared to a plate cured with an interrupted cycle, cured at 160 °C in the RTM tool to $\alpha = 0.8$ and then cured as described in Fig. 5; free standing in the oven. The intermediate α differs from the optimised curing cycle because these experiments were done at an early point in the project. From the thermal measurements, no difference between interrupted (B-stage) and isothermal cure can be detected. The results from the DSC measurements to obtain α and T_g are shown in Table 5.

Table 5. Shows the thermal properties of isothermal- and interrupted-cure CFRP plates.

Isothermal cure at 180 °C		Interrupted cure cycle	
α (-)	T_g (°C)	α (-)	T_g (°C)
0.94 ±0.01	211.8 ±3.0	0.93 ±0.01	212.3 ±1.3

Typical results of the single lap bearing tests for isothermal and interrupted cure CFRP parts are shown in Table 6. The values of the interrupted and the isothermal cured plates are comparable, suggesting that B-stage interruption has no effect on the mechanical performance of the final part. The same observations were made for mechanical tests on pure resin samples.

Table 6. Comparison of the bearing force, P_{max} , and bearing strength, σ_{brmax} , for isothermal and interrupted cure CFRP plates.

Isothermal cure at 180 °C		Interrupted cure cycle	
P_{max} (kN)	σ_{brmax} (MPa)	P_{max} (kN)	σ_{brmax} (MPa)
12.8±0.8	562±36	12.2±0.9	533±50

4.2 Bearing tests of patch reinforced samples

A first batch of eight patch reinforced, co-cured samples was tested in single lap bearing. The intermediate α was measured to be 0.5 ± 0.03 (instead of 0.7 due to temperature lag of the resin in the RTM tool) for the plate and 0.33 ± 0.04 (intended 0.3) for the patch. The samples were tested and compared to the unreinforced reference cured isothermally at 180 °C, giving the results shown in Table 7, where σ^{br}_2 and σ^{br}_{max} are the bearing strength at 2 % or at maximum bearing strain (ϵ^{br}_{max}), and P_{max} is the maximum bearing force.

Table 7. Results of the single lap bearing experiments.

σ^{br}_2 (MPa)	P_{max} (kN)	σ^{br}_{max} (MPa)	ϵ^{br}_{max} (-)
Reference			
588±44	16.5 ±1.1	730±51	0.15±0.03
Patch reinforced co-cured samples			
417±129	17.1±1.9	547±126	0.27±0.05

The average value of σ^{br}_2 is 30 % lower in the reinforced samples whereas the average value of P_{max} is 10 % higher than in the reference sample. The standard deviation in the reinforced samples is much higher than in the reference samples.

For better understanding of these results, typical load-displacement curves for an unreinforced reference and two patch reinforced samples are shown in Fig 7.

Fig. 7. Typical results obtained from the first bearing tests of patch-reinforced, co-cured samples

Where the stresses of the patch reinforced samples are lower than the reference, the maximum force may be increased when the patch does not delaminate (sample 1 in Fig. 7). The high variation in the results can be explained by two different observed failure modes, early delamination of the patch (sample 4 in Fig. 7) or compression of the patch after bolt rotation (sample 1 in Fig. 7). In Fig. 8 the effect of the adhesion is visible, showing a) a sample before the test, b) and c) sample 1 after the test, showing that a lot of deformation energy was absorbed by the patch, while in d) and e) showing sample 4, the patch delaminated early during the test and is much less deformed.

Fig. 8. Bearing samples a) before the test, b) and c) with good adhesion (sample 1), and d) and e) with bad adhesion (sample 4)

In the polished cross section of sample 1 with the good adhesion, shown in Fig. 9, a crack (arrows) caused by the compressive load of the bolt is progressing from the plate into the patch before delamination at the co-cured interface.

Fig. 9. Polished cross section of sample 1 with good adhesion, showing compression failure (arrows) progressing from part to patch.

This shows the good adhesion of the part and the patch, where the interface between them is not a weak region for initiating cracks.

4.2 Surface treatment study

After the big differences obtained in the adhesion in the first set of samples, a study of different surface treatments has been conducted. Plates with different release methods and surface treatments were cured

to an α of 0.7. The used method for producing the samples was as follows:

- 1) with a teflon release film on the surfaces to be co-cured while the rest of the tool was treated with a release agent.
- 2) All tool surfaces treated with release agent
- 3) Method 1) with the teflon film replaced with a Nylon peel ply
- 4) Method 2), sanded and acetone cleaned

The results of the XPS measurements of the samples for the different treatments are shown in Table 8.

Table 8. Results show XPS measurements of the surface of the composite.

Sample	Elements (Atom%)					
	C	N	O	F	Si	Ca
1 Teflon	69.3 ±0.4	2.7 ±0.2	10.9 ±0.6	12.6 ±1.0	3.8 ±0.4	0.8 ±0.1
2 Release agent	71.6 ±0.5	3.2 ±0.1	15.6 ±0.4	x	8.9 ±0.3	0.8 ±0.1
3 Peel ply	81.8 ±0.8	4.7 ±0.4	11.4 ±0.3	x	1.6 ±0.3	0.5 ±0.1
4 Sanding/solvent	83.0 ±0.9	4.6 ±0.9	9.9 ±0.8	x	1.3 ±0.2	1.2 ±0.2

From these results it is clear that the teflon foil (method 1) and the release agent (method 2) are a bad option, leaving a high amount of teflon and silicone residues, indicated by Fluorine (F) and Silicon (Si) which prevent adhesion to the surface of the CFRP part. The peel ply (method 3) and the sanding and acetone cleaning (method 4) give

almost the same results, but in both there are still traces of Si indicating silicone release agent residue. The only partially cured resin of the plate and patch is a challenging factor, especially in case of the patch with an α of 0.3. Since sanding or sand blasting could lead to inorganic particles embedded in the matrix surface, and most common solvents can diffuse easily in a partially cured network, method 4 was also not considered further.

As there are still traces of silicone found with method 3, the experiment was repeated with four different Polyester and Nylon peel-pplies. From those peel-pplies, a Nylon peel-ply showing no residues of silicone or teflon will be hereon used for further bearing experiments.

4 Conclusion

A full process for co-curing B-staged composite parts was successfully developed, including kinetic and T_g modelling of the curing reaction of an epoxy resin, simulation of curing cycles, development of the tools and optimising of the process. The simulation of the curing cycle shows that a free standing co-cure is possible, but that RTM 6 is not the most suitable resin for such a process (due to a very small process window). An ideal resin would have a preceding T_g , which means that T_g is above the curing temperature in a wide range of heating rates. Such resins are used for tooling and marine applications, where large structures are often post-cured outside of a mould. With a more suitable system, a wider range of possible B-stage values are available and the window for the process optimisation is larger.

The experiments comparing isothermal and interrupted cured plates indicate no difference in thermal and mechanical properties, suggesting that such a process may be an extremely viable and cost effective method of joining.

The effect of the co-cured patch on bearing strength was tested in a first series of samples. It was shown that the bearing force can be increased up to 20 % when the adhesion between the part and the patch is good. It was also found that with good adhesion the failure does not propagate along the part-patch interface, but progresses from the part into the patch.

The surface treatment study showed that the used method with a teflon foil was far from optimal treatment and will be replaced with an appropriate Nylon peel ply for future work.

With the suggested improvements in the sample curing and surface treatment, it is believed that the values of the bearing resistance of the patch reinforced composite will increase significantly.

This approach seems to have potential to produce co-cured structures when resin systems with preceding T_g are utilised.

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